

Experiment Design Report Assignment 2

Group 02

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1 Summary of the Chosen Paper

We have chosen a paper in the field of Information Retrieval with the title *A Study of an Automatic Stopping Strategy for Technologically Assisted Medical Reviews* which is written by Giorgio Maria Di Nunzio and presented in ECIR 2018, see [0]. Due to expanding numbers of published studies finding relevant documents to conduct a systematic review has become a time consuming task. This paper is focusing on determining an appropriate threshold to deal with the so-called total recall problem occurring from an active learning framework which is previously proposed by [2].

This previously published paper describes a two-dimensional BM25 model to find a cost effective solution for retrieving related documents in the medical domain. The described model approaches the problem of finding relevant documents as a two-class classification problem and defines two coordinates x and y represented by likelihood of being a document in the relevant or non-relevant class, respectively. Furthermore, the previous paper defines tuning parameters m and q to find an optimal separation line in the two dimensional space defined by x and y . It also investigates an improved set of parameters for the model and additionally assesses query formations, creates new queries based on the information need and finds an automatic stopping strategy for the retrieving process.

Our chosen paper is a continuation of the above-described work, in which the tuning parameters m and q are adapted iteratively based on an expert feedback regarding the relevance of each assessed document and to eventually be able to filter out the non-relevant documents in an automatized way. Particularly, the work is extended by including a stopping strategy with the following methodology;

1. A subset (percentage) of documents are chosen to be read and a threshold of maximum documents to be evaluated by an expert is decided.
2. BM25 scores of the documents are decided and the relevance feedback is obtained from the expert for the top ranked documents.
3. An interpolating line with parameters of m and q of the relevant documents are found, an additional line with the same slope passing through the least relevant document is found.
4. Repetition is started from step 1 if there are any un-judged documents exist below the second line.

5. The expert is asked to evaluate more documents if there are no un-judged documents exist until a certain ratio of non-relevant documents/ total number of judged documents are reached.

1.1 Experimental Setup and Data Set

Two data sets of the so-called CLEF eHealth 2017 task are used in this paper. The first set consists of 50 systematic reviews run by domain experts. There are 50 topics found, 20 of which are training and the remaining 30 are test data. A set of Pubmed Document Identifiers (PIDs) are found for each topic together with relevance feedback for documents and their abstracts. The second data set is used as baseline for the analysis. This data consists of 50 publicly available results of participants to the task¹ and can be found on [4].

The author used the same source code from [2], which is not publicly available and extended this work to investigate the affect of different combinations of percentage and threshold per document and only used the topics from the test data. The percentages in the above-described algorithm are increased from 10% to 50% by steps of 10% and the threshold is changed from 100 to 1000 by steps of 100. The paper records the recall for every combination of the corresponding parameter values. In addition, it selects five most promising runs of the automatic stopping strategy (associated with a threshold of 500) to compare them to the official results of the CLEF eHealth task (see Section 3).

In the following, 2 summarises our efforts to reproduce the model results of [0]. Afterwards, Section 3 uses the given data (i.e. model results) and R-code of [0] to analyse whether the stated claims in [0] are indeed valid in view of the provided model output and also stand up to a statistical analysis.

2 Reproducing Model Results

We selected this paper as a candidate to reproduce its results due to the following three reasons:

- clear and well explained methodology of the experiment,
- available data,
- available R code.

However, these elements were found to be partly misleading when they were thoroughly analysed. As a matter of fact,

¹This work at hand refers hereinafter to these results as “official results” of the CLEF eHealth task.

they do not suffice to neither automatically generate the results from the paper using the provided source code, nor to write codes based on the explained methodology to generate similar results.

Our efforts to replicate the results and the issues we have faced are documented in this section.

2.1 Methodology of the Paper

As explained in Section 1, this paper introduces a new methodology to retrieve the most relevant documents for a specific medical enquiry.

The author explains that the method merges a two-dimensional representation of probabilistic models with the BM25 model. The probabilistic model is explained in a prior paper [1] by the same author which is based on a costs-sensitive Naïve Bayes classifier. The relevance weight is decomposed into two terms that reflect the relevance in a geometric space based on another paper [2] by the same author. The two-dimensional representation translates the ranking into a geometric problem by selecting two parameters that separates the documents based on their relevance. The optimization of these parameters is described on another paper [3] by the same author.

The standalone paper [0] does therefore not suffice to fully explain and present the complete methodology, which is instead dissected into four different papers. Furthermore, the paper does not elaborate on the foundations provided in [1]-[3] but only references them. This complicates matters for us to reproduce the results and to comprehend the full methodology, especially because of the restricted access to some of these papers.

2.2 Data

The author provided a GitHub repository that includes some data. During the course of our assessment, we realized that the data only includes the results of the author’s runs and the runs of the 50 participants of CLEF 2017 (see Section 1.1). This data set does not include any original data that were used to generate the results.

The author refers to an explanation of data pre-processing in [2]. In the latter, the author decided to include more search terms in his queries which may improve the results. These queries were not available although they are an essential part to reproduce the author’s results.

Another aspect that is missing from the data is the feedback of the expert. Note that [0] uses relevance judgement provided by the expert after reviewing a certain threshold of documents that are initially classified as relevant (see the algorithm description in Section 1).

Even though we were able to find another GitHub repository that includes the testing data set which was used by all the participants at CLEF 2017, the lack of the afore-mentioned data does not allow a straight-forward replication of the results.

2.3 Source Code

The author provided a GitHub repository that included some source code. However, the source code available for this paper only allows to reproduce the plots of the paper. These plots are intended to compare the results of the author to the results of the other participants from CLEF 2017 (see Section 3). The code is therefore strictly limited and does not allow replicating any of the results and in particular all previous modelling steps in detail.

We tried to generate the two-dimensional BM25 model and the automatic stopping strategy from scratch by ourselves. However, as previously mentioned, the intricate methodology with numerous modelling steps to be replicated as well as the lack of data impeded us from producing any scientifically comparable results.

2.4 Additional Efforts

In order to obtain the missing code and the data we contacted the author via the email address provided in [0]. We asked him whether he is able to share the code of the underlying models and automatic stopping strategy. In addition, we also asked kindly for guidance on additional documents if necessary and available. Unfortunately, we have received the author’s feedback only after finalising this report. For that reason, we were not able to incorporate his offered help to reproduce the paper’s results.

3 Reproducing the Statistical Validity of the Claimed Results

In the paper [0], Figures 2, 3 and 4 summarise the results of the proposed automatic stopping strategy. The following paragraphs summarise the claimed results of the author. The following sub-sections 3.1-3.3 analyse whether we were able to reproduce the author’s claim based on the model output of the *provided data and R-code*. Note that we have provided R-code analyses_group02.R that we have written for these analyses. This code is primarily based on the provided R-code of [0] by only adding additional code lines for the relevant analyses. To identify these lines, each added code block starts with a distinct starting comment and ends with a specific ending comment. Furthermore, to more easily refer to the code of our analyses, each block has received an id in the starting comment to which the following sub-sections 3.1-3.3 refer.

Aggregating the shown documents and the average recall values of the 30 topics in the test sample, Figure 2 of [0] compares the results of the official runs of the CLEF eHealth task to the results of the proposed stopping strategy. The latter results depend on the chosen threshold and percentage of selected documents (see the algorithm in Section 1). The author claims that the proposed stopping strategy gives better results over all topics in the sense that they lie above the Pareto frontier of the official results. Furthermore, for recall

values greater than 0.95, the author’s solution uses 25,000 documents less than the best official results.

Figure 3 of [0] consists of two sub-figures 3a and 3b. For each topic of the test sample, Figure 3a displays the achieved recall values of all official runs of the CLEF eHealth task as boxplots. Conversely, Figure 3b uses boxplots to show for all topics of the test sample the recall values of all 50 runs of the proposed stopping strategy. Furthermore, Figure 3b includes blue lines to indicate the corresponding results of the selected five runs that use the automatic stopping strategy with a threshold of 500 judged documents per expert (the percentage of the selected documents varies from 10% to 50% in steps of 10%). The author claims that the “median recall per topic of the stopping strategy is consistently greater than the median of the official results, and the small interquartile range shows” that the automatic stopping strategy “can achieve a 100% recall with any combination of percentage and threshold.”

Figure 4 again consists of two sub-figures 4a and 4b. Figure 4a displays for each topic of the test sample the shown documents of the official CLEF eHealth runs (using boxplots) and the selected five runs of the automatic stopping strategy (blue lines). Figure 4b similarly compares the resulting average precision values per topic for the official CLEF eHealth runs (using boxplots) and the selected five runs of the automatic stopping strategy (blue lines). The author claims that “in general” the number of shown documents for the runs using the threshold of 500 judged documents is “in line with the median of the official runs, while average precision is greater than the values of the third quartile of the official runs.”

3.1 Scrutinizing Figure 2

In this subsection, we are going to analyse whether the above summarized claim of Figure 2 is valid.²

First, we are going to analyse whether the results of the proposed automatic stopping strategy are indeed above the Pareto frontier. By visual inspection, this seems to be the case for all relevant points. While five points (runids 1, 11, 21, 31, 41) with docs_shown around 17,000 and recall values of approximately 0.64 are very close to the Pareto frontier, we managed to verify that they are indeed above the frontier (using interactive figures of plotly and zooming into the relevant region).

Second and last, we are going to validate whether for high recall values (greater than 0.95), the author’s solution uses 25,000 documents less than the best official results of the CLEF eHealth task. For that purpose, we have filtered the author’s solutions for recall values above 0.95 and determined the maximum number of shown documents among the remaining solutions. We compared the resulting number of

²Please refer to code block id 1 in analyses_group02.R to reproduce our analyses.

63,073 documents with the minimum number of shown documents among the best official results of the CLEF eHealth task that give a recall value of more than 0.95. As this number amounts to 84,740 documents, the author’s claim seems to be not quite correct: for high recall values, the author’s solution uses around 21,000 documents less than the best official results.

Concluding, we were able to establish the author’s claim that his proposed automatic stopping strategy outperforms the official results of the CLEF eHealth task in the sense that the results of the automatic stopping strategy lie above the Pareto frontier. However, while we can also confirm that the author’s solution makes use of considerably less shown documents, we cannot reproduce the exact difference of 25,000 documents.

3.2 Scrutinizing Figure 3

In this subsection, we are going to analyse whether the above summarized claims of Figure 3 are valid.³

Based on Figures 3a and 3b, the author claims that the “median recall per topic of the stopping strategy is consistently greater than the median of the official results.” By analysing the provided data, we were able to establish the author’s claim in almost all cases. Still, in two out of 30 cases (topics CD010339 and CD011145), the author’s claim is not correct and the recall median of the official results is 8-10 percentage points greater than the author’s results (see Figure 1).

Regarding the second claim of the small interquartile range showing that the automatic stopping strategy “can achieve a 100% recall with any combination of percentage and threshold,” we can confirm that the interquartile ranges of the author’s solution are indeed smaller than the corresponding ranges of the official results. However, for five topics (CD009579, CD010339, CD010653, CD010783, CD011145), there does not always exist a setup of the proposed automatic stopping strategy (defined via a percentage of the selected documents and a threshold of the judged documents of the expert) that provides 100% recall. Still, the maximum recall values for these topics are very high (above 93 %).

Concluding, we were able to confirm in almost all cases that the median recall of the author’s solution is indeed higher than for the official results. While also the interquartile ranges are smaller, there exist some topics for which the author does not achieve 100% recall in any of the parameter setups.

3.3 Scrutinizing Figure 4

For Figure 4a,⁴ the author claims that the number of shown documents for the runs using the threshold of 500 judged documents is “in line with the median of the official runs.”

³Please refer to code block id 2 in analyses_group02.R to reproduce our analyses.

⁴Please refer to code block id 3 in analyses_group02.R to reproduce our analyses.

Figure 1. Boxplots show the official CLEF eHealth recall values per topic and the blue line indicates the median recall per topic of the proposed stopping strategy in [0]. The red figure elements indicate the topics for which the author’s claim of Figures 3a and 3b in [0] is not correct because the blue line is below the median of the official results.

Based on the provided data, we found that the median number of shown documents in the author’s approach is only for seven out of 30 topics smaller than the corresponding median number of the official results. For all other topics, the author’s approach requires (in median) 10%-245% more shown documents. Still, when assessing the mean number of shown documents, we were only able to establish for two topics (CD009647, CD009925) that the author’s approach requires on average statistically significantly more shown documents than the official results (confidence level 95%). Here, we used a two-sample t-test with Bonferroni correction to account for multiple testing.

Using Figure 4b,⁵ the author states that the “average precision” of his approach is “greater than the values of the third quartile of the official runs.” The provided data allowed us to verify that this claim is indeed correct for 20 out of 30 topics. For the other ten topics, the mean precision of the author’s approach is (in relative terms) 1%-60% smaller than 75% of the official runs. By using a one-sample t-test and Bonferroni correction, we were able to verify that this

⁵Please refer to code block id 4 in analyses_group02.R to reproduce our analyses.

difference is statistically significant for eight⁶ of these ten topics at a confidence level of 95% (see Figure 2).

Concluding, the author’s solution uses in most of the cases more documents than the official results. Still, for the predominant part of topics, this difference is not significant. Furthermore, in eight out of 30 documents, we were not able to reproduce the author’s claim that his solution provides a higher precision than 75% of the official runs.

Figure 2. Boxplots show the official CLEF eHealth precision values per topic and the blue line indicates the average precision per topic of the stopping strategy in [0] with a threshold of 500 documents. The red figure elements indicate the topics for which the author’s claim of Figures 4b in [0] is not correct because the blue line is significantly smaller than the third quartile of the boxplots.

4 Conclusion

While the chosen paper [0] provides data and R-code in a GitHub repository, it does not allow to rebuild the underlying models. Instead, it only provides the model outputs and the relevant code to generate the figures in [0]. While we have tried to rebuild the models from scratch, we have not succeeded due to the numerous modelling steps and intricate methodology that represent the basis for [0]. Instead, we have tried to scrutinise the claimed results of [0] based on the provided model outputs. As a result, we were able to confirm the author’s claims in most of the claims. However, we couldn’t reproduce some claims to their full extent. Most

⁶This concerns topics CD008760, CD009579, CD009786, CD010542, CD010633, CD010653, CD010775 and CD010860.

notably, we were not in a position to confirm that the author's proposed solution leads to a better average precision than 75% of the official CLEF eHealth results.

5 References

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